

Condensation of Dehydroacetic Acid with Diazonium Compounds

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In earlier communications^{1,2}, condensation products of dehydroacetic acid with several aryldiazonium chlorides have been reported. The present communication concerns with the condensation of various aryldiazonium chlorides with dehydroacetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dehydroacetic acid was synthesized from ethyl acetoacetate following Arndt's method with slight modifications³.

Substituted aromatic amines were diazotized in the usual manner and then added gradually with constant stirring to a well cooled alkaline solution of dehydroacetic acid. The mixture was allowed to stand for 1 to 2 hr. The compound which separated was filtered, washed with dil HCl and finally crystallized from ethanol.

The characteristics of the diazonium compounds are given in the table.

TABLE
Condensation of Dehydroacetic acid with diazonium compounds

Sl. No.	Diazotised Amines	Formula	Colour	M.P. °C	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	Yellowish	122	—	—	9.42	9.79
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅	Brown	142	—	—	9.48	9.72
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅	Violet	130	—	—	9.46	9.72
4.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxy aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅	Dark grey	160	—	—	9.48	9.72
5.	Anthranilic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₅	Light brown	210	—	—	8.61	8.85
6.	<i>o</i> -Nitro Aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	Brown	96	—	—	8.63	8.80
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitro aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	Grey	192	—	—	8.60	8.80
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitro aniline	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₆	Deep yellow	82	—	—	8.50	8.88
9.	<i>p</i> -Amino acetanalide	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅	Grey	215	—	—	8.42	8.51
10.	<i>p</i> -Amino salicylic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅	Grey	230	—	—	7.58	8.09
11.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅	Orange	188	—	—	9.00	9.23
12.	Sulphanilamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆ S	Reddish	132	8.82	9.11	—	—
13.	Sulpha thiazol	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	Red	220	14.40	14.70	—	—
14.	Sulpha pyridine	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S	Light brown	212	7.15	7.47	—	—
15.	Sulpha diazine	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₆ S	Light green	222	7.18	7.45	—	—
16.	Sulpha guanidine	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₆ S	Orange	218	7.66	8.11	—	—

Yield = 20 to 25%

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1. D. R. Gupta and R. S. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 421.
2. D. R. Gupta and R. S. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 377.
3. D. R. Gupta and A. C. Ojha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).

The yields of these compounds are generally low ranging from 20–25%.² All these compounds are soluble in methanol, ethanol, toluene, benzene and acetone but insoluble in water and alkali⁴. In these compounds, the presence of—OH group in ortho position with respect to the diazo group offer a possibility for being used as an analytical reagent for the estimation of metal ions.

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4. Migridichian, "Organic Syntheses", Vol. II, Reinhold Publishing Corporation, 1957, p. 1518.